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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
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A CASE STUDY OF HUMANITIES DISCIPLINES USING MASSIVE OPEN ONLINE COURSES AS A RESOURCE FOR BLENDED LEARNING

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Abstract: The prevailing trend in the advancement of online education, actively debated within the educational community, is learning through Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs). The primary determinant of the effectiveness of MOOCs in educational institutions is access to high-quality instruction. In contemporary circumstances, when lifelong learning has become essential, cultivating students' readiness for self-education is a particularly relevant task, one that MOOC platforms can substantially support. The integration of MOOCs has been widely examined in the context of higher and professional education; however, their implementation in school practice remains insufficiently addressed in pedagogical literature, which largely focuses on the natural sciences. This article analyzes MOOCs in the humanities and explores the application of blended learning models ("Flipped Learning," "Autonomous Group," and "Individual Trajectory") based on existing online courses. The findings indicate the need for further research in this area and for the integration of MOOC elements into the educational process in order to bridge the gap between the demand for individualized learning and the underutilization of available online resources.

Key words: e-learning, lifelong education, blended learning, instructional models, autonomous groups, flipped learning, individual trajectories, humanities education, MOOC, independent study, self-education.

Annotatsiya: Bugungi kunda ta'lim hamjamiyatida faol muhokama qilinayotgan onlayn ta'lim rivojlanishining ustuvor yo'nalishi ommaviy ochiq onlayn kurslar (MOOK) yordamida o'qitishdir. Ta'lim muassasalarida MOOKlardan foydalanish samaradorligini belgilovchi asosiy omil yuqori sifatli bilim olish imkoniyatidir. "Hayot davomida ta'lim olish" konsepsiyasi zaruriyatga aylangan zamonaviy sharoitda talabalarda mustaqil ta'lim olishga tayyorgarlikni shakllantirish dolzarb vazifa hisoblanadi va bu borada MOOK platformalari katta imkoniyatlar yaratadi. MOOKlarning integratsiyasi oliy va professional ta'lim kontekstida keng o'rganilayotgan bo'lsa-da, ularning maktab amaliyotiga joriy etilishi pedagogik adabiyotlarda yetarlicha yoritilmagan, bunda asosan tabiiy fanlarga urg'u berilgan. Ushbu maqolada gumanitar fanlar bo'yicha MOOKlar tahlil qilinadi hamda mavjud onlayn kurslar asosida aralash ta'lim modellaridan ("teskari ta'lim", "avtonom guruh" va "individual trayektoriya") foydalanish masalalari tadqiq etiladi. Tadqiqot natijalari ushbu sohani yanada chuqurroq o'rganish va ta'limni individuallashtirishga bo'lgan ehtiyoj hamda mavjud onlayn resurslardan yetarlicha foydalanilmaslik o'rtasidagi tafovutni bartaraf etish uchun MOOK elementlarini ta'lim jarayoniga tatbiq etish zarurligini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: elektron ta'lim, uzluksiz ta'lim, aralash ta'lim, o'qitish modellari, avtonom guruhlar, teskari ta'lim, individual trayektoriyalar, gumanitar ta'lim, MOOK, mustaqil ish, mustaqil ta'lim.

Аннотация: Доминирующим направлением развития онлайн-образования, активно обсуждаемым в педагогическом сообществе, является обучение с использованием массовых открытых онлайн-курсов (МООК). Ключевым фактором эффективности внедрения МООК в практику образовательных организаций выступает доступность высококачественного обучения. В современных условиях, когда концепция “образование в течение всей жизни” становится необходимостью, формирование готовности учащихся к самообразованию является особенно актуальной задачей, решению которой могут способствовать платформы МООК. Интеграция МООК широко рассматривается в контексте высшего и профессионального образования, однако их внедрение в школьную практику недостаточно освещено в педагогической литературе, где основное внимание уделяется естественным наукам. В данной статье проводится анализ МООК по дисциплинам гуманитарного профиля и исследуется применение моделей смешанного обучения (“перевернутое обучение”, “автономная группа” и “индивидуальная траектория”) на базе существующих онлайн-курсов. Результаты исследования указывают на необходимость дальнейшего изучения данной области и внедрения элементов МООК в образовательный процесс для устранения разрыва между потребностью в индивидуализации обучения и недостаточным использованием доступных онлайн-ресурсов.

Ключевые слова: электронное обучение, непрерывное образование, смешанное обучение, модели обучения, автономные группы, перевернутое обучение, индивидуальные траектории, гуманитарное образование, МООК, самостоятельная работа, самообразование.

INTRODUCTION

Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) are widely acknowledged as a preeminent trend in online education. The educational community emphasizes the supplementary learning opportunities they provide, including the dissemination of content by diverse knowledge bearers and significant organizational advantages. Researchers A. U. Mentsiev and S. V. Petukhova assert that MOOCs offer access to high-quality education, as courses developed by eminent scholars from the world's most prestigious institutions are now available to a broad audience.

This initiative aims to enhance the educational toolkit in order to promote accessibility for diverse categories of learners rather than to replace traditional academic disciplines. From this perspective, MOOCs function as a comprehensive instrument for implementing core instructional principles such as visibility, systematicity, scientific rigor, and accessibility.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The majority of contemporary research focuses on the integration of MOOCs into higher education, particularly for organizing autonomous extracurricular learning activities (A. V. Mironov, I. R. Bakulina, et al.). Researchers note that MOOCs increase student motivation and improve the quality of independent learning; however, their effective implementation requires well-prepared instructors with appropriate competencies. U. S. Zakharova argues that certain objectives, such as accessibility, are constrained by factors including limited awareness, insufficient technological infrastructure, and language barriers, especially the requirement for English proficiency. While some scholars contend that MOOCs are primarily beneficial for adult “lifelong learners” due to the high level of self-regulation required, this article maintains that these limitations should be regarded as challenges to be addressed rather than as deterrents to the adoption of MOOCs in educational institutions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Historically, Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) originated in the field of Information Technology, subsequently expanded into the natural sciences, and only later encompassed the humanities. Within the humanities, MOOCs are predominantly applied to foreign language instruction, whereas documented experience in disciplines such as history or Russian as a foreign language remains limited. Research on the application of MOOCs in educational practice, particularly in the humanities, is scarce. Nevertheless, positive outcomes have been reported in the field of physics (T.E. Khochenkova et al.). As a result, a clear dichotomy has emerged: educational institutions increasingly require diversification and personalized learning trajectories, while the substantial potential of existing MOOCs remains largely underutilized in general secondary education.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Surveys conducted within the framework of this research, involving 20 educators and 152 students, revealed a pronounced “awareness gap”: only 15% of educators and 5% of students were familiar with the concept of MOOCs. Furthermore, merely 1% of students had previously used a MOOC platform for studying humanities-related subjects. To address this issue, the study identifies several blended learning strategies. The

flipped learning model presupposes that students familiarize themselves with new theoretical material through MOOCs at home, while classroom time is devoted to active and practice-oriented activities. In this model, educators employ platform analytics tools, such as the “Gradebook” function available on Stepik, to identify learning gaps prior to classroom sessions.

The autonomous group model involves dividing the class into groups according to differing cognitive and educational needs. One group may utilize MOOCs to prepare for Olympiads or the Unified State Exam (EGE), while other groups engage with alternative educational resources. The individual trajectory model positions MOOCs as a self-directed learning resource for advanced students or those requiring targeted remediation. In this context, the instructor assumes the role of an educational manager who monitors progress and provides guidance. The analysis highlights several available digital resources suitable for educational institutions, including the course “History Lessons at School” on the Stepik platform authored by L.G. Voronina; social studies courses designed for EGE preparation developed by D.V. Polyansky and L.G. Voronina; the course “Russian Language: Simply About Words” created by linguistics specialist Y. Makarova; the literature-oriented course “Ghosts of St. Petersburg” hosted on the Lektorium platform and authored by V.V. Razumets, which offers an engaging literary exploration; and the specialized training course “Olympiad Practicum in Social Studies” developed by RANEPa and delivered via Lektorium.

CONCLUSION

The number of students engaged in online or blended learning formats is steadily increasing. Educators prioritize ensuring access to high-quality digital educational resources. MOOCs foster self-directed learning skills, which are essential for a smooth transition from secondary education to higher education and for life-long learning, as stipulated by the Third Generation Federal State Educational Standards. However, the effectiveness of MOOCs in developing communicative and professional competencies requires further investigation. The primary objective for the academic community is to strengthen the methodological preparedness of humanities educators for the effective implementation of blended learning approaches.

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 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
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